

Information Transfer Cycle for Online Journal Articles

By

Trisha Das

F.W. Lancaster showed how information is transferred from the user community to the publishers, and again to the user community. It is a cyclic process depicted in Figure 1. This shows how **written information** is created and assimilated by the users. By getting an influence from his Information Transfer Cycle (ITC), we can create an ITC for online journal articles.

According to **Lacaster**, the **user community** comprises both users (people who need information for study or work in a particular subject area) and individuals engaged in Research & Development activities. **Authorship** means a person who writes down the information he/she discovered or created. The written work is officially published for the first time (e.g., journal, book, thesis, report, etc.) which is known as the **primary publication**. The newly published material is now shared or sold directly to the user community or readers, which is known as **primary distribution**. Next, **acquisition** is done by libraries, other kinds of information centres, which collect and store the published material. They also **organised** the information using indexing, cataloguing, classification and related procedures, so that it becomes easy to retrieve. Sometimes information is summarised or

republished again (e.g., indexes, abstracts, bibliographies, review articles); which can be considered as **secondary publication**. In **secondary distribution**, these information summaries help users to locate needed material from larger collections. The final stage in the cycle is **assimilation**. This, the least tangible, is the stage at which information is absorbed by the user community, i.e. they read, understand and uses the information for learning, research or creating new knowledge. Thus, the cycle repeats.

❖ Stages of Information Transfer Cycle for Online Journal Articles :

The following sections provide an in-depth analysis of each stages of the above **information transfer cycle for online journal articles** :

1. User Community :

Here, as Lancaster's ITC, the **user community** comprises users, who need information for study or work in a particular subject area.

2. Creation of information :

Creation means to generate new information or knowledge through different types of research, experiments, analysis or creative processes. This stage comprises of conception, execution, and documentation of original research.

3. Manuscript Preparation :

After creation of information, the manuscript of that information is created or prepared by Microsoft Word, typesetting system like- LaTeX, XML, PDFs etc.

4. Metadata Capture :

Structured metadata (e.g., author ORCID Ids, keywords, abstracts) is created for the ease of retrieval.

5. Submission of Articles :

Manuscripts are then submitted via online editorial management systems, like- ScholarOne, Editorial Manager, Open Journal Systems, Janeway as open-source software etc.

6. Collection/Selection :

Articles are then selected and collected in different publisher websites, like- Elsevier, Springer, Wiley or academic databases and aggregators like JSTOR, PubMed, Web of Science, Scopus etc. or Institutional repositories, open access repositories (DOAJ etc.), search engines etc.

7. Indexing :

Documents are then indexed through- Scopus, Web of Science, Google Scholar, PubMed, Semantic Scholar, openAIRE, Proquest etc.

8. Primary Publication :

After indexing, documents or articles are then published By Open Access Publishers- PLOS, MDPI, research sites, like- ResearchGate etc.

9. Secondary Publication :

Sometimes information are summarised and republished again or after indexing, a secondary publication is done via different online journal platforms, institutional repositories, social media or academic networks like- academia.edu etc.

10. Organization :

Organization refers to the systematic arrangement and representation of information to facilitate discovery, retrieval, and use. This involves cataloguing, classification, indexing, and the assignment of metadata . After primary and secondary publication of articles, these are organised by descriptive metadata (titles, authors, abstracts, keywords, etc.), administrative metadata (rights, licensing, etc.), technical metadata (MeSH, LCSH) and ORCID and CrossRef.

11. Storage :

Storage involves the collection and preservation of information for future access and use. In the digital age, storage encompasses a range of electronic repositories and preservation strategies. The documents are stored in institutional repositories, public platforms, archives, cloud storage etc.

12. Dissemination :

Dissemination of information Is the process of distributing knowledge and information to the target audience through various platforms. It is usually done by UI/UX designers, API developers etc.

13. Retrieval :

Retrieval is the process by which users can easily locate an access information, relevant to their information needs. This is the main stage in Information Retrieval System. Retrieval can be done by different types of search strategies (Boolean search, truncation search, proximity search, range search etc.), full-text search, advanced ranking algorithms, faceted search, filtering etc.

14. Assimilation :

In this process, information is absorbed by the user community, i.e. they read, understand and uses the information for learning, research or creating new knowledge.

15. Evaluation & Feedback :

After assimilation of information, users evaluate the relevancy of information and provide feedback.

16. R & D Activities :

Sometimes evaluation of information creates new research ideas; which leads to research and development activities. Further, it transfer to the user community and thus the cycle repeats.

Conclusion

The Information Transfer Cycle for online journal articles shows how information moves from readers to researchers and then back again in a repeating loop. In today's digital world, the different stages of this cycle is described; where each step plays an important role. Authors create new knowledge, publishers make it available, digital libraries and databases organise and store it, and search tools help users to find what they need. When users read and understand the information, they may get new ideas. These ideas can lead to new research, and the whole cycle starts again.

In simple terms, this cycle helps make sure that knowledge is created, shared, used, and then turned into more new knowledge. It keeps information flowing smoothly in the academic world and supports continuous learning and research.

References

- Lancaster, F.W. (1979). *Information retrieval systems: Characteristics, testing and evaluation* (2nd ed.). New York: Jhon Wiley & Sons.
- Wiley Author Services. (n.d.). Focus on your content, not on formatting it. Retrieved from <https://authorservices.wiley.com/author-resources/Journal-Authors/Prepare/manuscripts.html>